

TENSILE FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The tensile fatigue life and failure mechanisms of 3D woven fibre-polymer composites are investigated. 3D woven fibreglass composites with different amounts of through-thickness reinforcement were fatigue tested under cyclic tension-tension loading. The initiation and accumulation of fatigue-induced damage was monitored over the life by determining changes to the elastic modulus of the composites. The fatigue properties of the 3D woven composites are compared to a 2D woven laminate containing a similar volume content of load-bearing fibres. The tensile fatigue performance of the 3D woven composites are inferior to the 2D woven laminate, however the reduction in fatigue endurance is independent of the amount of z-binder yarn content.

KEYWORDS: 3D woven composites, fatigue, tensile properties, damage mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

3D woven fibre-polymer composites are emerging as versatile materials with potential structural applications in aircraft, ships, civil infrastructure and armour protection [1]. 3D woven composites consist of in-plane layers of warp and weft fibres woven together with z-direction fibres to provide through-thickness reinforcement. The z-binders are highly effective at improving the delamination toughness, impact damage resistance and post-impact mechanical properties of composites [2-6]. Even a relatively modest amount of through-thickness reinforcement can provide a substantial improvement to the impact damage tolerance, and therefore most 3D woven composites have a low z-binder content (typically under 5%).

A problem commonly experienced with 3D woven composites is the z-binder can degrade the in-plane mechanical properties due to out-of-plane crimping and distortion of the load-bearing fibres. Numerous studies have shown the in-plane tensile, compressive and flexural properties of 3D woven composites are reduced by the z-binder [7-12]. However, the effect of the z-binder on the fatigue performance of 3D composites has not been studied in detail. Dadkhah et al. [13] investigated the fatigue behaviour of 3D woven carbon/epoxy composites under cyclic compression-compression loading. It was found that crimping of load-bearing yarns by the z-binder causes kinking of the fibres that leads to fatigue failure. However, Dadkhah et al. did not compare the fatigue performance of the 3D woven composites against a 2D laminate to determine the reduction in the fatigue life caused by the z-binder. Ding and Jin investigated the performance of orthogonal 3D woven composites subject to flexural fatigue loading [14]. They found that 3D woven composites exhibited superior delamination resistance leading to improved flexural fatigue performance. As yet the fatigue properties of 3D woven composites under cyclic tensile loading has not been determined. Tensile fatigue studies performed on other types of 3D composites, namely stitched and z-pinned laminates, have found a large reduction to the fatigue life due to the through-thickness reinforcement [15, 16]. It is essential that the fatigue performance of 3D woven composites be characterised because of their potential applications in structures subjected to cyclic tensile loading.

This paper presents preliminary research into the tensile fatigue endurance and failure mechanisms of 3D woven composites. The effect of increasing z-binder content on the fatigue life of a 3D woven composite is examined. The 3D composite was woven using E-glass fibres, and this material was studied because of the potential use of 3D fibreglass composites in non-aerospace structures.

3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

3D fabric preforms for the composites were woven from E-glass yarns using a computer controlled Jacquard loom. The weaving process used to manufacture the preforms is described by Lee et al. [17]. The preforms were woven with an orthogonal fibre structure that is shown schematically in figure 1. The preform contained six layers of warp yarns and seven layers of weft yarns, and these were bound together by through-thickness binder yarns. The linear density of the warp and weft yarns was 900 Tex and 1200 Tex, respectively. The density of z-binder yarns was 68 Tex, 204 Tex or 408 Tex to produce 3D composites with 0.3%, 0.5% or 1.1% reinforcement, respectively.

Figure 1. Idealised schematic of the fibre structure to the 3D woven composites.

Figure 1 shows the idealised fibre structure of the 3D woven composites, but in reality the structure was characterised by several types of defects caused during weaving. Firstly, the z-binder yarns did not exactly follow the profile shown in figure 1. During weaving it is necessary to apply a slight tensile load on the z-binders to ensure they remain taut when woven into the preform. The load causes the z-binders to follow a sinusoidal-shaped profile rather than the square-wave profile depicted in figure 1. This distortion to the z-binder profile is commonly experienced in 3D woven composites [1, 11, 12]. The tensile load on the z-binders also causes crimping of the in-plane yarns at the surface. The effect of crimping is shown in Figure 2 where the weft yarns are crimped by the binder and the warp yarns are indirectly crimped via the weft yarns.

The 3D woven preforms were consolidated with a vinyl ester resin (Derakane[®] 411-C50 from Dow Chemicals) using vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM). After VARTM, the 3D composites were held under pressure at a cure temperature of 110°C for one hour followed with a six hour post-cure at ambient temperature under platen pressure. Table 1 shows the volume content of resin and warp, weft and z-binder yarns to the 3D composites. In addition, a 2D laminate containing plain woven glass fabric was fabricated using the same VARTM process and curing conditions as the 3D composites. This material was made to compare the fatigue behaviour of a typical 2D woven laminate against the 3D woven composites. The fibre content of the 2D laminate is given in table 1, and it contained a similar

volume fraction of load-bearing warp yarns to the 3D woven composites so the fatigue properties can be directly compared.

Figure 2. Schematic of crimping of a surface yarn by a z-binder. Reproduced and adapted from Cox et al. [10] with permission from Pergamon Press.

Table 1. Fibre and resin contents for 2D and 3D woven composites.

Composite	Resin V_m	Total Fibre V_f	Warp V_f	Weft V_f	Binder V_f
2D woven	0.608	0.392	0.196	0.196	0
3D 0.3% Binder	0.476	0.524	0.213	0.308	0.003
3D 0.5% Binder	0.473	0.527	0.209	0.312	0.005
3D 1.1% Binder	0.459	0.541	0.211	0.319	0.011

STATIC TENSILE AND FATIGUE TESTING

Static and fatigue tensile tests were performed on the 2D and 3D woven composites using rectangular specimens that were 250 mm long, 25 mm wide and about 3.8 mm thick. The static tensile tests were performed at a loading rate of 0.5 mm/min to determine the Young's modulus and tensile strength. The fatigue tests were performed under constant amplitude, sinusoidal tension-tension loading. The tests were performed over a range of peak fatigue stress levels ranging from 20% to 90% of the static tensile strength of the composites. An R ratio of 0.6 and loading frequency of 2 Hz was used in all tests. The fatigue tests were continued until the composite failed, at which point the number of cycles to failure was recorded. In some tests the composites did not fail, and in these cases the test was stopped after 1,000,000 load cycles. During fatigue testing a clip-on extensometer (with a gauge length of 25 mm) was used to continuously record the change to the elastic modulus of the composites. In this work, failure is defined by complete rupture of the composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the effect of z-binder content on the Young's modulus and tensile strength of 2D and 3D woven composites. Despite some scatter in the tensile properties, it is apparent that the modulus and strength of the 3D woven composites is not influenced significantly by the z-binder. The 2D woven composite shows a slightly reduced Young's modulus compared with the 3D woven composites whereas the strengths are similar. The slightly lower Young's modulus for the 2D woven composite may be the result of a lower weft volume fraction, since the weft fibres contribute to the stiffness but not necessarily the strength.

Despite the scatter in results, there appears to be no clear correlation between z-binder content and tensile properties. This is in agreement with the observation by Tong, Mouritz and Bannister [1] that the tensile properties of 3D woven composites are not strongly influenced by their z-binder content up to ~10%. Based on a review of published tensile property data for 3D woven composites, Tong et al. [1] concluded that the elastic modulus and strength is usually improved or reduced by less than 20% by the through-thickness reinforcement. Mouritz and Cox [18] discovered a similar effect for 3D stitched composites, where the reduction to the tensile properties showed no clear correlation to the z-binder content. The mechanism by which the z-binder reduces the mechanical properties of the 3D woven composites is not yet fully understood. Previous studies of the tensile properties of 3D woven composites suggest that the degradation is due to crimping and distortion of load-bearing fibres by the z-binders as well as the introduction of new crack initiation mechanisms around the binder yarn [12, 19].

Figure 4. (a) Young's modulus and (b) Tensile strength of 2D and 3D woven composites (N=4, error bars = ± 1 SD).

Figure 5 shows fatigue life (S-N) curves measured under cyclic tensile loading for the 2D and 3D woven composites. The peak fatigue stress is expressed as a percentage of the tensile strength for that material. These strength values are given in Figure 4. It can be seen that the fatigue performance of the 3D woven composites is inferior to the 2D woven laminate with a similar amount of load-bearing fibres. This is a concern because it reveals that a relatively modest amount of through-thickness reinforcement can degrade the fatigue life.

Figure 5. Fatigue-life curves for 2D and 3D woven composites.

Comparing the S-N curves for the 3D woven composites it can be seen that there is little change in fatigue performance for specimens with 0.3% z-binder and 0.5% z-binder content. However, there is a noticeable reduction in fatigue performance for the 3D woven composite with the higher z-binder content of 1.1%. This indicates that there is only a slight correlation between z-binder content and fatigue performance over the narrow range of z-binder contents studied. However, it is proposed that increasing the amount of z-binder to a much higher level may cause an appreciable reduction in fatigue performance.

The mechanism by which z-binders reduce the fatigue performance of 3D woven composites has not yet been identified, although research into the fatigue damage mechanisms is continuing. However, insights into the fatigue process can be gained by plotting changes to the Young's modulus of the composites as a function of time. Figure 6 shows typical reductions to the elastic modulus of 2D and 3D woven composites over the duration of their fatigue life. The 2D woven composite displays softening of ~6% during stage I ($N/N_f \leq 20\%$) of fatigue life. This observation is consistent with the behaviour reported for many types of 2D composite materials [20, 21], and Talreja [21] reports that this is caused by the formation of transverse matrix cracks. The elastic modulus of the 3D woven composite also decreased during the initial stage of the fatigue life, however the reduction was only around 2%.

Figure 6. Reduction in Young's modulus over the fatigue life for 2D and 3D woven composites. (Peak fatigue stress is 70% of the static tensile strength).

Figure 6 shows that when the 2D woven composite reached stage II, or 20% of the fatigue life, the rate of modulus reduction decreased significantly. Again this is commonly observed for 2D laminates, and signifies that the material has reached the characteristic damage state whereby no further transverse matrix cracks can be produced by fatigue [20, 21]. During this stage other types of fatigue damage occur, such as longitudinal crack coupling whereby transverse cracks are 'blunted' by the fibres and are reoriented along the longitudinal direction, usually in the form of fibre/matrix debonding [20]. The 3D woven composite also experienced a reduction in rate of damage accumulation during stage II, but the gradient of the curve does not 'flatten' as much as the curve for the 2D woven composite. It is proposed that the presence of the z-binder promotes crack-coupling, therefore the rate of damage progression during stage II of fatigue life is slightly higher for the 3D woven composite than for the 2D woven composite. This hypothesis is based on the experimental observation that the cross-over point between the z-binder and weft yarns provides a site for crack-initiation and fibre/matrix debonding during static tensile testing [12].

Near the end of their fatigue life the elastic modulus of the 3D and 2D woven composites drops sharply, and this is due to the fracture of load-bearing fibres that quickly leads to complete tensile fatigue failure.

CONCLUSIONS

This study is a preliminary investigation of the tensile fatigue performance and damage mechanisms of 3D woven composites. It was discovered that the Young's modulus and tensile strength of the 3D composites were not affected significantly by the amount of z-binder reinforcement over the narrow range studied here. However, the tensile fatigue life of 3D woven composites was reduced significantly by the z-binders. The fatigue performance of the 3D composites was inferior to a 2D woven composite with a similar content of load-bearing fibres.

The accumulation of fatigue damage in 3D woven composites was monitored indirectly by changes to the elastic modulus. It appears that fatigue damage in 3D composites develops in a similar way to conventional 2D laminates, and probably consists of transverse matrix cracks, crack coupling leading to fibre/matrix debonding, and finally fibre fractures that causes tensile fatigue failure. At this stage the reason for the differences in damage

progression between 2D and 3D woven composites is not established. Microstructural analysis of the 3D woven composites at different stages of their fatigue life is in progress to identify the fatigue damage mechanisms.

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